

Revealed preferences over experts and quacks and failures of contingent reasoning

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Abstract

In many economic scenarios, people resort to different tests to obtain information about the payoff-relevant states of the world. This paper studies how people evaluate and choose between useless tests (quacks) and genuinely useful ones (experts). Using a novel graphic experiment, I recover individual preferences over tests. I find people fail to distinguish between experts and quacks. Their quack choices are not driven by standard explanations, including belief updating bias, best-responding bias, and intrinsic preference of information. The main culprit is the failure in reasoning the contingency value of tests for their decision problems.

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1 Introduction

Imagine a decision-maker, DM hereafter, bets on the result of a race between two horses (L and R) to win a prize. The DM first checks the performances of two horses in the past 100 races, and she learns that horse L won 60 times, and R won 40 times. In addition, the DM can consult a horse analyst, obtain a recommendation for one of the two horses, and then choose the bet. Suppose an analyst correctly predicted 42 (70%) times among the 60 races in which horse L won and 18 (45%) times among the rest 40 races in which horse R won, should she solicit a recommendation from this analyst? When there are several such analysts, varying in prediction accuracies, to whom should the DM resort, and how much should she pay the chosen analyst before receiving a recommendation?

These questions are common for many decision scenarios. People choose among competing clinic doctors, diagnostic tests, financial advisors, and news sources to figure out the payoff relevant states of the world. I generically call them “tests”.¹ They are not the decision-guiding signals per se but describe the process of how such signals are generated. This fundamental difference determines the DM evaluates tests before she actually acquires a piece of information — people have already chosen a horse analyst or a medical test when they receive race predictions or clinic diagnoses. If a test is ex-ante useless, I refer to it as a *quack*, and similarly, an *expert* test is ex-ante useful.

This paper studies how people choose and evaluate quack and expert tests. I first establish the theoretic framework for tests and the associated decision problems. The usefulness of a test, defined as the expected benefit for the decision problem from having or not having the test, is a joint output of decision problem-specific characteristics (e.g., prior information, test structure, and available actions), agent-specific characteristics (e.g., individual preferences and beliefs), and their interactions (e.g., reasoning process). Consider the particular analyst in the horse race example. If consulting him increases the probability to win the prize from the prior, he is an expert, and the probability increment measures his usefulness. Since the analyst’s prediction is unknown at this point, a standard DM assesses the “expected” winning probability — a weighted average of the winning probability when conditioning on the analyst’s prediction being l or r , respectively. Such a measure of test usefulness implicitly assumes that the DM an-

¹They are also called experiment (Blackwell (1951)), information structure (Green and Stokey (1978)), or information source in the literature.

anticipates all possible signals, correctly formulates posterior beliefs for each signal and thus best-responds in bet choices, and more importantly, learns how does the test structurally interact with beliefs and optimal bet choices.

The evaluation process of tests implies four major channels leading to the failure in distinguishing quacks and experts. They include (1) the DM is unable in *updating beliefs* as a Bayesian; (2) she makes *sub-optimal choices* given her beliefs; (3) she has an *intrinsic preference* over certain types of tests; and (4) she lacks *contingent reasoning* in how the value of a test changes with its influence on beliefs and optimal actions.

Using a novel graphic experiment, I elicit people's preferences over tests and examine how they are explained by the aforementioned channels. Individuals face fourteen decision problems, each analogous to the horse race example, winning a prize through a bet on state L or R . Before the bet decision, they see a coloring representation of a set of tests, and they move sliders to control color compositions and select their favorite tests. The choice set in each problem consists of both expert and quack tests. They are on a common linear budget with two accuracies as two commodities, reflecting trade-offs between receiving good news in one state versus in the other. I construct fourteen budgets with multiple prices and expenditure levels. They generate rich variations both within and across the choice set of tests, and thus I can identify different decision rules. Given the chosen test, subjects also estimate the likelihood of two states and make bet choices. These auxiliary tasks are part of the incentive schemes of choosing an instrumentally valuable test, and on the other hand they elicit people's posterior beliefs and strategies for the evaluation of tests. Altogether, the experiment is user-friendly and provide diagnoses of different mechanisms.

I find people fail to distinguish experts and quacks on a large scale. Subjects frequently select useless tests at the aggregate, decision problem-wise, and individual level. The failure is *not* driven by belief updating bias, best-responding bias, or intrinsic preferences over certain types of tests. Subjects' reported posteriors are very close to Bayesian posteriors, and they rarely choose sub-optimal bets. Moreover, none of the variables measuring belief bias or action sub-optimality explains quack versus expert choices. I also construct test-specific and posterior-specific measures to capture subjects' preferences over several test characteristics. I find they have similar distributions between the group of experts and quacks, excluding intrinsic preferences as a channel for quack choices.

I also find that people are over-paying for quacks but accurately paying for experts. In particular, given the chosen test is an expert, subjects correctly identify the most useful expert; while given a quack test, they choose the most distant quack (the quack test with one accuracy equals to either zero or one). Based on subjects' descriptions of their decision processes, I identify three simple rules employed to evaluate tests and further establish their roles in causing such a pattern. These rules reflect subjects' reasoning in resolving overall uncertainties (*entropy-reducing rule*), discriminating processes of evidence generation (*evidence-separating rule*), and polarizing the chances of two signals (*signal-separating rule*). All of them justify "extreme" tests on a budget, leading to the pattern of choosing either the optimal expert or the distant quack. However, they cannot fully rationalize the choice of quacks versus experts.

The above two findings confirm a universal bias in reasoning when a test is useful. I refer to the bias as *the failure of contingent reasoning in information processing*. It occurs when subjects fail to recognize that the value of a test depends on its influence on the associated decision problem. This bias hinges on a simple intuition: when a test induces posteriors support the same action for different signals, the test is a quack; otherwise, it is an expert.² In the horse race example, the DM bets horse L under the prior belief that horse L has a 60% chance to win the prize. When faced with the analyst with the accuracy pair (70%, 45%), a Bayesian DM's posterior belief is 66% over state L after a signal l and 50% after r . Both posteriors support the same bet on horse L , indicating this particular analyst is a quack. From the ex-ante perspective, the DM's chance to win the prize remains the same as the prior due to the law of iterated expectations.

This paper contributes to a growing literature on preferences over information structures. A bulk of work consider the case when information is non-instrumental. Falk and Zimmermann (2016), Ganguly and Tasoff (2017), and Nielsen (2018) study the intrinsic preference over test informativeness through preferences over the timing of information and the resulting resolution procedures of uncertainty. They find people typically prefer to receive the decision-irrelevant information sooner.³ Masatlioglu, Orhun, and Raymond (2017) provide evidence for an intrinsic preference over positively-skewed information structures. In the setting when infor-

²Early work such as Hirshleifer (1971) has already noticed the insight that information can be useless if it does not impact choices. Recently, Lara and Gossner (2020) exploit the bilinear duality structure between payoffs and beliefs to study the value of information in the same spirit.

³Theoretical work on the preferences over early versus late resolution and gradual versus one-shot information include Kreps and Porteus (1978), Loewenstein (1987), Epstein and Zin (1989), Grant, Kajji, and Polak (1998), Dillenberger (2010), and Ely, Frankel, and Kamenica (2015).

mation is instrumentally valuable, Ambuehl and Li (2018) find that people undervalue expert tests due to belief updating biases. Charness, Oprea, and Yuksel (2018) and Montanari and Nunnari (2019) study how people choose between prior-confirming and contradicting information structures, and they find people prefer confirming ones at the cost of informativeness. I consider a framework for both instrumentally useless (quacks) and useful (experts) information structures and study whether people can differentiate them. Moreover, I focus on people's reasoning biases that lead to failures in identifying experts and quacks.

This paper also contributes to the literature on the failure of contingent reasoning. It often describes people's inability in recognizing the optimal actions for all possible contingent states or their opponents' actions.⁴ An agent without contingent reasoning ability cannot identify dominant strategies. Therefore, many studies on contingent reasoning are the same as on the empirical validity of the dominant strategy in different games and mechanisms. Tversky and Shafir (1992) make subjects play one-shot prisoner's dilemma games and find people have trouble realizing that their dominant strategy does not rely on opponents' choices. Cason and Plott (2014) find people do not report truthfully (even though it is a dominant strategy) under the Becker, DeGroot, and Marschak (1964) (BDM) elicitation mechanism. Harstad (2000) finds people fail to identify the dominant strategy in the sealed-bid second-price auction even after sufficient learning opportunities. Esponda and Vespa (2014) show similar mistakes in a common-value voting experiment. Chen (2008) reviews such evidence for the context of public good provision.

Esponda and Vespa (2019) generalize the state space for strategic games and formally define the failure of contingent thinking as violating Savage (1972)'s sure-thing principle. They also experimentally show such failures are robust across several decision problems and games. In this paper, I identify a different form of contingent reasoning. The contingencies are on information structures, not on states. More precisely, the state-contingent failures occur since the DM is not partitioning the states between those where her choice does matter and those where it does not. While the test-contingent failures occur since the DM is not partitioning the information structures between those with which her optimal strategies are pooling across signals and those with which are separating. Such failures have a significant implication for how people seek out information sources, how data sellers provide information products, and the general information design problems.

⁴Martínez-Marquina, Niederle, and Vespa (2019) consider the contingent reasoning implied in the strategic requirement of subgame perfect Nash equilibrium. That is, people cannot correctly foresee how others behave for all contingencies, no matter they will arise or not.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the theoretical framework for expert and quack tests and their values. Section 3 describes the experiment to elicit preferences over tests. In Section 4, I present the experimental results on failures in distinguishing and evaluating experts and quacks. Section 5 examines the mechanisms behind these failures, and Section 6 discusses extensions and implications of my findings. Section 7 concludes.

2 Theoretic framework for expert and quack tests

2.1 Setup: states, signals, and tests

The DM faces a decision problem with two states of the world $\omega \in \{L, R\}$ and two actions $a \in \{L, R\}$. Each action corresponds to a bet on the state, yielding a payoff of π if it matches the true state and zero otherwise. I denote the objective prior belief of state L by a scalar μ and assume $\mu \in [1/2, 1)$. The DM may also resort to a test for a signal $s \in \{l, r\}$. The signal is potentially informative for the inference of the true state. Each test governs a generation process of signals, and the DM chooses a test before knowing the signal to be generated. Analogy to the horse race example, I define a test as a pair of two state-contingent probabilities (accuracies) and denote it by (p, q) , in which $p \equiv \mathbb{P}(s = l \mid \omega = L)$ and $q \equiv \mathbb{P}(s = r \mid \omega = R)$. I consider a collection of tests satisfying $p \geq 1 - q$. That is, the probability of signal l under state L is at least as large as that under state R . I call such tests *admissible*, and they are in the set denoted by $\mathcal{T} \equiv \{(p, q) \mid p + q \geq 1, 0 \leq p, q \leq 1\}$.⁵

How to choose the optimal bet for the decision problem? I assume the DM is probabilistically sophisticated as in Machina and Schmeidler (1992). In my setup, it simply says that the DM's preference is consistent with her beliefs. Therefore, her optimal action is to bet the state she thinks has at least a fifty percent chance to occur. This assumption admits the DM being a non-expected utility maximizer. For example, the DM may transform her belief probabilities with a strictly increasing function as in Tversky and Kahneman (1979) and Tversky and Kahneman (1992). The threshold for the belief is fixed at one half, under which the DM is indifferent between two bets. This threshold is invariant of the information environment characterized by the prior, the signal, and the test and is exclusively determined by

⁵This set partitions the test space $[0, 1] \times [0, 1]$ into halves and is rich in capturing all possible posterior distributions. It is symmetric to the tests in the other half of the partition, and all theoretic analyses remain the same by swapping two signals.

the symmetric payoff structure of two bets. Doing so removes the influence of the preference over outcomes and leaves all the analyses within the probability space. The DM's utility over outcomes may be linear, concave, or convex, but she always chooses the optimal bet by comparing her belief of each state with the threshold. In section 6, I discuss how my setup can be easily extended to decision problems with alternative payoff structures.

A test affects the optimal bet by inducing a distribution of posterior beliefs over the state. Given a prior μ , I denote the posterior induced by a particular test (p, q) by a scalar $\mu_s(p, q; \mu)$, which is the DM's belief of state L after signal s . Before knowing the signal, the DM treats the posterior as a random variable with two realizations $\{\mu_l, \mu_r\}$. The probability mass of each realization is the unconditional probability of the corresponding signal $\mathbb{P}(s)$. Provided the signal s , the DM's optimal action is to bet state L whenever the posterior belief after the signal is larger than one half and to bet state R otherwise, and thus she believes that her chance to win the prize is $\max\{\mu_s, 1 - \mu_s\}$. Since the DM does not know whether the signal is l or r yet, she takes expectation of these two signal-contingent winning chances. Let $v(p, q; \mu)$ denotes the *ex-ante* expectation of the probability to win the prize, we have

$$v(p, q; \mu) = \max\{\mu_l, 1 - \mu_l\} \mathbb{P}(s = l) + \max\{\mu_r, 1 - \mu_r\} \mathbb{P}(s = r).^6$$

The defined winning chance provides a criterion to evaluate and compare different tests. When there is no test, the DM bets L and expects to guess the state correctly with a chance equals to the prior. The difference between $v(p, q; \mu)$ and prior μ measures how useful the test is to the decision problem from having or not having the test. A quack test leads to a zero increment in the chance to win the prize, and an expert test leads to a strictly positive one. The increment summarizes how much extra "certainty", compared to that under prior knowledge, the DM gains from the test. For a given prior, I simply define the *value of a test* as the expected winning probability $v(p, q; \mu)$. Notice that the DM's interim decision-making elements, precisely, her belief updating process and action best-responding, root in this measure. When there are several tests available, the DM should choose a test she thinks has the largest increment in the expected winning probability. Equivalently, she is selecting a distribution over posterior beliefs that guides her bet choices the most.

⁶Notice that posterior μ_l and μ_r are mappings from the admissible set \mathcal{T} to $[0, 1]$. The unconditional probabilities of signal l and r also depend on the test (p, q) and the prior μ .

2.2 Distinguishing experts and quacks in a rational benchmark

Consider the benchmark of a *rational* DM who updates as a Bayesian and best responds to her Bayesian posteriors. Due to the martingale property of Bayesian updating, any arbitrary test will induce a mean-preserving posterior spread of the prior. Moreover, if a test is admissible, its Bayesian posterior of state L after signal l is no smaller than that after signal r . The vice versa also holds. Proposition 1 formalizes the idea.

Proposition 1. *An admissible test induces a Bayesian posterior spread such that observing signal l (or r) increases the posterior of the state L (or R) relative to the prior, and vice versa. Mathematically, for any prior μ , a test $(p, q) \in \mathcal{T} \iff \mu_r^{Bayes}(p, q; \mu) \leq \mu \leq \mu_l^{Bayes}(p, q; \mu)$.*

A rational DM will bet state L if the signal realization is l . Given the prior is in favor of state L ($\mu \geq 1/2$), this strategy is consistent with her posterior belief over state L being larger than one half.⁷ When the signal is r , she compares the corresponding Bayesian posterior with the threshold of one half. If it is larger than one half, she bets state L and wins the prize with a chance of μ_r^{Bayes} ; otherwise, she bets R and has a chance of $1 - \mu_r^{Bayes}$. Taking expectations of these two contingencies, a rational DM's ex-ante winning probability of the prize is

$$v^{Bayes}(p, q; \mu) = \mu_l^{Bayes} \mathbb{P}(s = l) + \max \{ \mu_r^{Bayes}, 1 - \mu_r^{Bayes} \} \mathbb{P}(s = r).$$

Whether a test is an expert or a quack rests on μ_r^{Bayes} , the induced posterior belief after signal r . If it is smaller than one half, the test is an expert; otherwise, the test is a quack. Intuitively, a test is useful only if it induces posteriors that support alternative optimal actions for the decision problem, instead of the same one indicated by the prior. Proposition 2 states the condition that distinguishes expert and quack tests. Moreover, it shows the value of each expert test is a linear combination of two state-specific accuracies, with prior beliefs as their weights. This assessment is empirically convincing. When an expert is not able to predict the true state for sure, people evaluate his expertise based on a weighted average of his prediction accuracy for each state.

⁷I assume the DM will choose action L when her posterior beliefs over two states are the same. Under my construction of priors and admissible tests, the indifference scenarios with a Bayesian posterior of $1/2$ after signal l only occurs when the prior is $1/2$, and the test satisfies $p + q = 1$. Notice the Bayesian posterior after signal r also equals to $1/2$ for these scenarios. Therefore, all analyses will not be affected by this indifference-resolving procedure.

Proposition 2. Given a rational DM and a prior μ , an admissible test (p, q) is an expert (a quack) if and only if the condition $(1 - p)\mu - q(1 - \mu) < 0$ is (not) satisfied. The value of an expert test is $v^{Bayes}(p, q; \mu) = p\mu + q(1 - \mu)$, and the value of a quack test is μ .

Figure 1a plots the partition of experts and quacks. The prior is three fifths. Each point lying above the diagonal line is an admissible test, with the x -axis coordinate as the accuracy for state L and that on y -axis for state R . The parallel dotted lines are a rational DM's indifference curves over experts' accuracies p and q . They share the same slope $\mu/(1 - \mu)$, which is the prior odds of state L versus R . One indifference curve (blue) partitions the admissible space into two sets, one corresponds to quack tests (stripped area) and the other one to experts (crosshatched area). For an arbitrary prior μ , the partitioning indifference curve is characterized by $q = \frac{\mu}{1-\mu}(1-p)$ and has two fixed points (μ, μ) and $(1, 0)$. The partition line under a larger prior will pivot around point $(1, 0)$ towards northeast, generating a larger set for quack tests. It implies that when the prior is already very informative for the state, more tests are quacks as it is more difficult to improve the chance to win the prize.

Figure 1: (a) A rational DM's indifference curves and partitions of experts and quacks; (b) an example of two linear budgets used to elicit preferences over tests. The prior is fixed at three fifths. The x -axis is the conditional probability of signal l under state L , and the y -axis is the conditional probability of signal r under state R . The numbers on top are the values of tests on depicted indifference curves.

2.3 Eliciting preference over tests via linear budget sets

In practice, people’s indifference curves over tests may be non-linear. For instance, if a DM has a preference for tests with a large difference between two accuracies, her indifference curves will be convex. However, all indifference curves are downward sloping regardless of their shapes.⁸ They reflect how people make trade-offs between two state-contingent accuracies. To compare two tests, one with a higher p and the other with a higher q , the DM is trading off the probabilities to receive good news from state L versus R .⁹ In other words, people’s preferences over tests are revealed through their choices of the accuracy bundle (p, q) when faced with trade-offs between p and q . I follow this idea and elicit people’s preferences over tests via linear budgets $p + mq = z$, wherein m is the relative price, and z is the accuracy expenditure. Each linear budget is a choice set of tests, and the DM selects her most preferred alternative, knowing that each one percent increase in accuracy q implies a decrease of m percent in accuracy p .¹⁰

Figure 1b illustrates two linear budgets, XY and EF . The former budget is steeper than the indifference curves of a benchmark DM, and the latter one is flatter. They interact at the symmetric quack test U . Such construction ensures that U divides both budgets into two segments, one for experts and one for quacks. Meanwhile, experts are lying on the upper segment for budget XY and on the bottom segment for budget EF . When the slope of the budget is larger than that of indifference curves, like in the case of XY , the commodity q is relatively cheaper. Therefore, it is optimal to choose the accuracy bundle X with $q = 1$. Similarly, the commodity p is relatively cheaper on EF , making F the most useful expert. I examine whether people can distinguish experts and quacks by the location of the chosen test being on the expert segment or not. The deviation of the chosen test from the optimal one, on the other hand, investigates whether people are over-paying for quacks and under-paying for experts.

I choose particular pairs of budgets such that for each expert on one budget,

⁸The downward sloping indifference curves for experts implicitly assume the preference over test accuracies are monotonic and non-satiated.

⁹When there are no trade-offs between two tests, one must be at least as accurate as the other one for both states. The value for the former one is no smaller than the latter. In particular, the former one is Blackwell more informative than the latter when they are experts.

¹⁰Equivalent formulations include the trade-offs between a type I and type II statistical error or between the false positive rate and true positive rate. The later one is also the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve (Hanley and McNeil (1982)), which is extensively used for the validity of a diagnostic test in clinical decisions. Chan, Gentzkow, and Yu (2019) empirically estimates the radiologists’ skills based on their diagnosis accuracies under the ROC framework. My study provides experimental evidence on the determinants of ROCs through a linear approximation.

there is a unique test on the paired budget having the same value. For instance, consider test M and N . They are equally valuable but skew to different state-specific accuracies. They also induce posteriors differing in spreads, skewness, or entropy. With such budget pairs, I can identify people’s intrinsic preferences over certain test characteristics and examine the associated decision rules. I can also study the relationships between people’s intrinsic preference and preference over tests for their instrumental value.¹¹

The linear budget approach is widely used in experimental literature to measure people’s preferences in various settings, for instance, their altruism preferences under the dictator game (Andreoni and Miller (2002)), social preferences over efficiency and equity behind the veil of ignorance (Heufer, Shachat, and Xu (2019)), risk preferences (Choi, Fisman, Gale, and Kariv (2007), Choi, Kariv, Müller, and Silverman (2014)) over two state-contingent assets, and time preferences (Andreoni and Sprenger (2012)) over current and future payments. With a rich choice set and an intuitive representation of trade-off problems, this approach allows for robust inferences from the elicited preferences. In addition, it provides a framework to apply the classic nonparametric revealed preference techniques (see Afriat (1967) and Varian (1982, 1983)) to examine whether preferences are standard.

3 Experimental design

3.1 Tasks

The experiment consists of fourteen decision problems. In each problem, subjects choose their most preferred test from a budget set in order to bet the state correctly. Table 1 lists the priors and budget specifications for all problems in the experiment. They show up in a random order. Each row gives a budget pair consisting of a steep and a flat budget, and they interact at a symmetric test, just like budget XY and EF show in figure 1b. I refer to the interaction point as a “Pivot” point. For each pair in the top five rows, pivot points are quack tests that coincide with priors. For budget pairs on the bottom two rows, the pivot is a fixed expert test $(3/4, 3/4)$. Figure 8 in Appendix B depicts all budgets in the accuracy space.

¹¹Subjects in my experiment can choose on a full budget. Since steep budgets intersect the diagonal line, the tests below the diagonal line are not admissible. However, all theoretical analyses are still valid. For such choices, receiving signal l (r) will increase the posterior of state R (L) from the prior. Since the state of L is advantageous in prior, all of these non-admissible tests are quack tests

No.	Prior	Steep budget	Flat budget	Pivot
P1	1/2	$2p + q = 3/2$	$p/2 + q = 3/4$	1/2
P2	3/5	$2p + q = 9/5$	$5p/4 + q = 27/20$	3/5
P3	3/5	$4p + q = 3$	$7p/8 + q = 9/8$	3/5
P4	2/3	$4p + q = 10/3$	$3p/2 + q = 5/3$	2/3
P5	3/4	$6p + q = 21/4$	$5p/2 + q = 21/8$	3/4
P6	3/5	$6p + q = 21/4$	$5p/2 + q = 21/8$	3/4
P7	2/3	$6p + q = 21/4$	$5p/2 + q = 21/8$	3/4

Table 1: Fourteen budgets used in the experiment

I develop a new interface to implement the choice of tests. Instead of making subjects choose on an abstract budget as in the literature, I present the decision problem as a graphic coloring task. Figure 2 shows the screenshot for a typical choice round. Box L and R at the top-left corner contain some labeled balls. Later all balls will be filled into Box A , and one ball (called Ball A) will be randomly drawn from it. A participant wins ten pounds if correctly betting the label of Ball A . The setting resembles the horse race example. The proportion of L balls in Box A indicates the prior probability of state L . Before putting all balls into Box A , the participant can color some balls in Box L and R by two sliders below the boxes. Moving a slider to the right (left) will increase the number of red (white) balls in the corresponding box. The step for the increments for each box is indicated above the slider. The initial locations of two sliders are determined by the pivot point, reflecting a default option of a symmetric test.

Choosing a color composition for two boxes is equivalent to choosing a test on a linear budget. First notice the number of balls in Box L and R imply the prior belief of each state. The red ball serves a signal realization of l , and the white ball is r . The proportion of red balls in Box L is accuracy p , and the proportion of white balls in Box R is q . The trade-offs between two accuracies are achieved by linking two sliders such that the colored balls in box L and R increase (decrease) with each other. For instance, in this particular round, every time the participant adds three red balls for Box L (p increases), five red balls will be automatically added to Box R (q decreases). More details about the construction of two boxes and their steps for each budget can be found in Table 11 in Appendix B.

The top-right corner of the interface shows what Box A looks like for the chosen color composition. When subjects move sliders, Box A 's coloring changes accordingly. With such interaction, it is clear to subjects that the color choices are instru-

Round 1 out of 14

Task 1. Choose color compositions for Box L and Box R

Box L: 120 Balls

Box R: 80 Balls

Box A: 200 Balls

step: 3

step: 5

The current composition of Box A is:

L	L	R	R
81	39	5	75

Show balls

Snapshot

Confirm color composition

Task 2. Bet on the label of "Ball A" if knowing its color

If "Ball A" is red, label is ?

I bet that its label is:

L	R
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I think the likelihood of its label being L vs. R is:

L: 86%	R: 14%
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If "Ball A" is white, label is ?

I bet that its label is:

L	R
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I think the likelihood of its label being L vs. R is:

L: 33%	R: 67%
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Next Round

Figure 2: Experimental interface for a typical decision round

mentally valuable. The state is not realized yet and their color choices matter for the correct guess of the state. I also provide an animation with the colored and labeled balls bumping with each other. It visualizes the random process of signals and states, and thus will remove subjects' suspicions about how uncertainties are resolved and how their payoffs are determined in the experiment.

After choosing the color composition, participants provide likelihood estimates

for the true state and their bet choices conditional on each one of the signal realizations. They are shown as Task 2 at the bottom of the interface. These auxiliary answers provide direct evidence on the mechanisms underlying people’s preferences over tests. In particular, the likelihood estimates measure people’s posterior beliefs, and the bet choices indicate whether people are best-responding given their beliefs. Notice that they are not separated from task of choosing tests. They determine the process to resolve the signal and the state and play an important role in the incentives of the test choice. If Ball *A* turns out to be red, the participant will be rewarded for her estimates and bet choices conditioning on the signal of red.

I present the belief updating task with natural frequencies and provide additional incentives for Bayesian posteriors. Given a color composition, the task of providing likelihood estimations is very similar to Grether (1980)’s “urn-and-ball” experiment. However, I avoid all descriptions of probabilities and present states and signals in frequency formats. For example, subjects can check the numeric composition of each type of balls in Box *A* when formulating posteriors. The frequency format describes a direct and convincing process about how the signal is naturally sampled and how the random state is resolved. Gigerenzer and Hoffrage (1995) show that the natural frequency formats substantially improve (up to 50%) Bayesian inferences than probability formats in several thousand Bayesian problems. Also, subjects are rewarded for being close to a Bayesian. The participant is told that a mathematician is facing the same color composition and also providing an estimate for the state. If the absolute difference between her estimate and the mathematician’s is smaller than five percent, she will earn a bonus of one pound and a half; if otherwise, the absolute difference is lower than fifteen percent, the bonus is fifty cents. This incentive scheme is straightforward to subjects.

3.2 Procedures

I ran the experiment in March 2020. A total of 64 subjects were recruited on Prolific platform.¹² The average payment was £7.25, not including a show-up fee of £4. Average duration of the experiment was 45 minutes.

Before the main task, subjects need to read the instructions (see Appendix D) carefully and complete a quiz. The quiz questions are not trivial. On average,

¹²To mimic the lab session, I imposed the pre-screening conditions including the age, undergraduate or master student, English proficiency, ect. In general, their choices are comparable with the those from the pilot session in the lab.

subjects spent 18 minutes on instructions and quiz questions, and it is similar to that of the pilot lab session.

After the experiment, one problem is randomly selected for payment. Subjects see a summary screen (see Appendix D) showing all information relevant for their payoffs: the random round selected for payment, the color and the label of ball *A*, their coloring choices, likelihood estimations and bets in that round, and the estimations from a Bayesian mathematician. I ask them to share thoughts about how they chose the color composition and the bets.

The final part of the experiment is a questionnaire that includes questions regarding demographic variables, self-evaluated psychological attitudes, and measures of cognitive reasoning. I consider three commonly used psychometric tests: Frederick (2005)'s cognitive reflection test (CRT) for the tendency to use heuristics, Wason (1968)'s selection task for the measurement of deductive reasoning, and logic-based Syllogism questions.

4 Experimental results

This section reports experimental results on subjects' choices of tests. In particular, I examine whether they can distinguish expert and quack tests on linear budgets and whether they are choosing the most useful experts. Figure 3 provides an array of scatter plots for four subjects' choices and budget sets. Subject 15 and 50's choices, in the top row of the array, exhibit a taste for tests with intermediate accuracies. However, most of Subject 15's choices are on the expert segments, while Subject 50 chooses tests on the quack segments for over half of the budgets. Subject 22 and 41, whose choices are in the bottom row, prefer tests on the border. Subject 22 is able to recognize the useful one between two border tests, and Subject 41 is not. Overall, subjects are heterogeneous in their preferences over tests, but they frequently choose quacks.

I proceed by providing statistical examinations of subjects' choices at the aggregate, decision problem-wise, and individual level. These results demonstrate that subjects fail to distinguish expert and quack tests on a large scale.

Figure 3: Illustrative examples of actual test choices and optimal ones. The budgets for P1-P5 and P6-P7 are shown in separate panels. The steep budgets are in red and the flat ones are in blue. Solid triangles show the subject’s actual choices of (p, q) , and hollow circles show the optimal ones.

4.1 The failure in distinguishing experts and quacks

At the aggregate level, subjects frequently choose quack tests. Table 2 reports the frequencies of quacks and experts across different budget pairs. The frequency of quack choices is 35% for all decisions, and it is significantly different from the average chance if randomly selecting tests on the same set of budgets (41%). Around 20% of subjects’ choices are on the quack segments of budgets in P1, P6, and P7. These budget pairs on average admit fewer quack tests.¹³ If we exclude them, subjects choose quack tests 47% of the time, and it is again significantly different from the random chance (62%) for budgets in P2-P5.

	Quack	Expert	Total
P1-P7	286 (35%)	526 (65%)	812
P1	24 (21%)	92 (79%)	116
P2-P5	219 (47%)	245 (53%)	464
P6-P7	43 (19%)	189 (81%)	232

Table 2: Frequencies of quack and expert choices

¹³For instance, almost all tests (except the symmetric one) on budgets in P1 are experts. There is no quack test for the flat budgets in P6 and P7.

Figure 4a plots the average rate at which subjects choose quack tests for each budget. Though the rate varies, subjects frequently choose quacks for almost all budgets. Nonetheless, they are not choosing randomly. They still identify experts more often than a random DM for most of the budgets.¹⁴ In general, steep budgets induce more quack choices than flat ones.¹⁵ However, a steep budget has a larger segment of quack tests than a flat budget, and therefore is easier for subjects to make mistakes in choosing quacks. After controlling the random chance of each budget, two types of budgets are not significantly different in predicting quack choices.

Figure 4: The histogram of quack choices and border choices for fourteen budgets. Points with cross markers in the left panel are a random DM's frequencies of selecting quack tests. The category of "expert-low" in the right panel indicates the non-optimal border choices for the flat budgets in P6 and P7. They are the least useful expert tests for these budgets.

The quack choices are also pervasive among all subjects in the experiment. They select quack tests for around five out of fourteen decision problems. Each participant chooses quack tests at least twice, and over half of them choose four times. Subjects on average still beat a random DM in recognizing expert tests. Individual frequencies of quack tests are significantly different from the random chance of selecting a quack test.¹⁶

¹⁴For ten out of fourteen budgets, the proportion of quack choices is significantly different from the corresponding random chance. The four budgets with insignificant results are the flat budget in P2 and P5 and two budgets in P4.

¹⁵The test is based on a probit regression with the binary quack choices as dependent variables and the binary budget type as independent variables. The estimate shows that steep budgets have 25% more chances in predicting quack choices than flat budgets. The difference is significantly different from zero, with a p-value of 0.0325.

¹⁶The p-value is 0.0002 for the Wilcoxon rank-sum test and 0.0008 for the t-test. If not specified,

4.2 The failure in evaluating experts and quacks

I continue to examine what kind of quack and expert tests subjects choose. Are the quack choices consistent with specific decision patterns or simply driven by trembling hands? Are the chosen expert tests the most useful ones? I define a participant's evaluation of a test as its distance deviation from the optimal test on the same budget. This deviation measures the opportunity cost of choosing the test by giving up the optimal one. A substantial deviation means that the subject is over-paying for the test. Since each budget differs in slopes and lengths, I normalize the deviation as a fraction of budget length. A deviation of zero means the choice itself is the optimal test, and a value of one implies the test is on the non-optimal endpoint of the budget.

The average deviation across all subjects and all budgets is 0.41, suggesting that subjects' choices are far from the most useful expert tests. However, its distribution uncovers a significant polarization in test choices. 41% of choices have zero deviations, and 26% have deviations of one. This result means that subjects overwhelmingly prefer tests that are endpoints of a budget. I call them border tests. When such test choices are on the optimal border, subjects are choosing the most useful experts; otherwise, they are choosing the most distant quacks.

Table 3 further summarizes three categories of subjects' choices: border, center, and interior test. Aside from border choices, subjects choose center tests which have symmetric accuracies 14% of the time. The rest 19% of choices are categorized as interior tests. The bottom two rows of the table show the test categories for expert and quack choices. Over half of the subjects' choices are on the border, regardless of their usefulness. Furthermore, 72% of border tests are the most useful expert tests, and this proportion is significantly different from the chance of one half.

	Border	Center	Interior	Total
Pool	544 (67%)	113 (14%)	155 (19%)	812
Quack	154 (54%)	78 (27%)	54 (19%)	286
Expert	390 (74%)	35 (7%)	101 (19%)	526

Table 3: Frequencies of three categories of test choices

all tests reported in this section are based on t-test, Wilcoxon rank-sum test for unpaired variables, Wilcoxon signed-rank test for paired variables, or proportion test. I will not report p-value if it is smaller than 0.0001.

The category results at both the decision problem and individual level further confirm the findings. Figure 4b plots the proportion of border choices and its compositions of experts and quacks for each budget. Subjects uniformly prefer border tests, and within the category, their choices are more likely to be expert tests for most of the budgets.¹⁷ At the individual level, subjects choose border tests nine times on average, and over one third of subjects choose border tests at least twelve times.

What are the consequences of choosing quacks or non-optimal expert tests? I compare the expected Bayesian winning probabilities of subjects' actual choices and those of the optimal tests. Subjects' test choices entail a chance of 0.684 to win the prize on average, which is significantly smaller than the one if they choose optimally (0.720). The average winning probability is 0.647 for quack choices and is 0.704 for expert choices, and they are significantly different from each other. This difference is also economically significant under my judgment. In my experiment, the prior probability to win the prize is already high (0.626), and thus it is not easy to improve the winning chance through test choices.

How much subjects can benefit in winning the prize if choosing optimally? Table 4 lists the summary statistics of the relative improvement. It is the percentage increment in winning probabilities of the most useful expert test compared to that of the actual chosen test. Since the majority of the expert choices are already on the correct border, there is not much improvement for them. However, subjects who choose quack tests will increase the winning chances by 11.6% on average.

	mean	sd	pt5	pt25	pt50	pt75	pt95
Pool	5.6%	0.074	0%	0%	3.3%	8.3%	21.5%
Quack	11.6%	0.077	3.3%	6.7%	8.3%	16.7%	24.0%
Expert	2.3%	0.047	0%	0%	0%	2.5%	12.7%

Table 4: Relative improvements in winning probabilities if choosing optimally

¹⁷For nine out of fourteen budgets, the proportion of expert choices within the border category is significantly different from the chance of one half. The five budgets with insignificant results are the flat budget in P2 and budgets in P4 and P5.

5 Mechanisms

In this section, I discuss the mechanisms behind quack choices. After choosing a test, each participant in my experiment also provides a likelihood estimate of the true state and chooses a bet for each signal realization. This auxiliary task measures how the participant evaluates the test she chose before, and thus provides diagnoses for different channels contributing to quack choices.

5.1 Unexplained mechanisms

5.1.1 Belief updating bias

I first investigate whether subjects are Bayesian and whether their updating biases cause quack choices. In the experiment, subjects will earn a step-wise bonus if their reported posterior of the chosen test is close to the Bayesian posterior. Table 5 provides the category of subjects' posterior estimates based on their bonus scales. Subjects are generally Bayesian. 79% of their reported posteriors for both red and white signal are five percent away from the Bayesian ones and thus are entitled to earn a bonus of £1.5. Another 14% of posterior estimates deviate from the Bayesian posteriors by at most fifteen percent and earn a bonus of £0.5. The incentive scheme works equally well for red and white signal.¹⁸

The belief updating deviates cannot explain quack and expert choices. Table 5 also displays the interaction between updating categories and test choices for each signal. When the signal is red, the posterior deviates of quack and expert tests are not significantly different. But they are significantly different after the white signal.¹⁹ The composition of the category of small deviates indicates that subjects are more likely to under-estimate state L under expert tests. However, it is mainly driven by how experts and quacks are defined, not by subjects' updating abilities.

Figure 5 illustrates the distinction between posteriors after the red and white signal. Each panel plots subjects' posterior estimates of state L on the y -axis against the Bayesian posteriors on the x -axis. The dashed lines are from the linear regressions, and the solid lines are from polynomial LOESS (Locally Estimated Scatter-

¹⁸The distribution of posterior deviates after red signal is not significantly different from the one after white signal, under both the Wilcoxon signed-rank test and the t-test.

¹⁹The p-value is 0.0095 under the Wilcoxon rank-sum test and is 0.0145 under the t-test. The result is also valid for absolute deviations.

		Small deviates			Medium deviates	Large deviates
		Bayes	over	under		
Aggregate		26%	24%	29%	14%	7%
Quack	red	76	69	80	34	27
	white	126	62	40	42	16
	pool	35%	23%	21%	13%	8%
Expert	red	97	132	177	78	42
	white	122	133	176	73	22
	pool	21%	25%	34%	14%	6%

Table 5: Classification of subjects' posterior estimates. All posteriors are on state L . Category of small deviates include observations that absolute differences between the reported posteriors and the Bayesian posteriors are no larger than five percent. Observations in the category of medium deviates have absolute differences no larger than fifteen percent. Category of "under" means subjects under-estimate state L , and posterior observations over-estimate state L is classified into the category of "over".

plot Smoothing) regressions. Both of them are very close to the identity lines, indicating that subjects are inferring signals as a Bayesian. When the signal is white, Bayesian posteriors for quacks and experts cluster on the separate side of one half. This cluster is consistent with the definition of quacks and experts — a test is a quack if it induces a posterior supports a bet on state L and is an expert otherwise. The lower magnitudes of posteriors for expert tests may contribute to the under-estimation result.

A formal estimation further confirms these findings. Columns (1) and (2) in Table 6 report the estimated coefficients and robust standard errors, separately for each signal. The dependent variable is the reported posteriors, and the independent variables are the Bayesian posteriors and a dummy variable for the quack test. The slope for the Bayes posterior is 0.90 and 0.91 for red and white signal, respectively. Both are very close to one, indicating that subjects are generally Bayesian.²⁰ The coefficients for the interaction terms are not significant for both signals, implying that Bayesian updating bias does not result in quack choices. Since the updating process may also cause the test choices, I use the binary variable of budget types as an instrument for the quack dummy.²¹ The estimation results are in

²⁰I cannot reject the null hypotheses that the slope is equal to one under the χ^2 -test. The p value is 0.005 for red signal and is 0.004 for white signal.

²¹The first stage Probit regression shows that a steep budget is highly predictive for quack choices. Having a steep budget, versus a flat one, increases the probability of quack choices by 0.470, with a standard error of 0.065.

Figure 5: Subjects' reported posteriors versus Bayesian posteriors. Shaded regions are 95% confidence intervals for Linear and LOESS regression.

columns (3) and (4). Again, their slope coefficients are close to one, and interaction terms are not significant.

To further investigate how the prior and the chosen test affect posterior beliefs separately for quack and expert choices, I update Grether (1980)'s regression and estimate the following model:

$$\ln \frac{\mu_{ij}(L | s)}{\mu_{ij}(R | s)} = \beta_0 \times D_q + \beta_1 \ln \frac{\mu_j}{1 - \mu_j} \times D_q + \beta_2 \ln \frac{\mathbb{P}_{ij}(s | L)}{\mathbb{P}_{ij}(s | R)} \times D_q + \epsilon_{ij}.$$

The dependent variable is subject i 's posterior odds after signal s in decision problem j . The independent variables include the prior odds for the same problem j , the likelihood ratio under i 's chosen test, and a dummy equal to one if the chosen test is a quack. The interaction terms capture whether quacks and experts induce the same extent of specific bias regarding priors and tests. When the subject is Bayesian, the coefficients for both prior odds and likelihood ratio are equal to one. Based on these comparisons, I consider four updating biases (see Benjamin (2019)). The coefficient of prior odds determines whether the subject has a bias of base-rate neglect ($\hat{\beta}_1 < 1$) or confirmation bias ($\hat{\beta}_1 > 1$). The coefficient of likelihood ratio determines whether the subject has under-inference ($\hat{\beta}_2 < 1$) or over-inference ($\hat{\beta}_2 > 1$) bias.

	<i>Dependent: subjective posterior</i>				<i>Dependent: ln(subjective posterior odds)</i>									
	OLS		IV		OLS		IV		Split sample: OLS		Split sample: IV			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	P1	(9)	P1	(10)	(11)	(12)
Constant	0.08*	0.02*	0.09**	0.02	0.19	-0.09	0.33*	-0.44**	0.16	0.18	0.20	-0.74**	0.42*	-0.75**
quack	(0.03)	(0.01)	(0.03)	(0.01)	(0.16)	(0.13)	(0.14)	(0.11)	(0.14)	(0.15)	(0.12)	(0.13)	(0.17)	(0.16)
steep(IV)	0.06	0.03			0.14	0.33**				0.33		1.10**		
	(0.04)	(0.03)	-0.01	0.01	(0.13)	(0.12)	-0.18	0.71**		(0.18)		(0.28)	-0.16	0.92**
Bayes posterior			(0.04)	(0.03)			(0.14)	(0.13)					(0.19)	(0.18)
Bayes posterior × quack	0.90**	0.91**	0.88**	0.95**										
	(0.04)	(0.03)	(0.04)	(0.03)										
Bayes posterior × steep(IV)	-0.08	-0.05												
	(0.06)	(0.06)	0.005	-0.05										
			(0.05)	(0.07)										
ln(prior odds)					0.99**	1.01**	0.81**	0.59**		0.99**		0.40*	0.70**	0.26
ln(prior odds) × quack					(0.15)	(0.14)	(0.17)	(0.16)		(0.16)		(0.18)	(0.23)	(0.21)
ln(prior odds) × steep(IV)					-0.24	0.01				-0.47		0.78**		
					(0.24)	(0.21)				(0.27)		(0.25)		
ln(likelihood ratio)							0.14	0.63**					0.11	0.80**
ln(likelihood ratio) × quack					0.91**	1.39**	(0.22)	(0.22)					(0.29)	(0.27)
					(0.04)	(0.04)	0.90**	1.46**			0.96**			
ln(likelihood ratio) × steep(IV)					-0.04	-0.25**	(0.03)	(0.04)			0.86**			
					(0.05)	(0.06)					(0.12)			
ln(likelihood ratio) × steep(IV)							0.01	-0.37**						
							(0.04)	(0.07)						
ln(likelihood ratio)										1.07**		1.57**	1.05**	1.55**
ln(likelihood ratio) × quack										(0.04)		(0.04)	(0.04)	(0.04)
ln(likelihood ratio) × steep(IV)										-0.05		-0.37**		
										(0.06)		(0.07)		
Observations	812	812	812	812	812	812	812	812	116	696	116	696	696	696
Adjusted R ²	0.71	0.77	0.71	0.78	0.75	0.83	0.75	0.83	0.45	0.75	0.64	0.84	0.74	0.84

Note: ·p<0.1; *p<0.05; **p<0.01

Table 6: Regression results for Bayesian updating bias. Robust standard errors (in parentheses) are clustered at the individual level. Odd columns are estimated with observations after red signal, and even columns are for white signal.

Table 6 reports the estimate results in columns (5)–(8), two for OLS, and the other two for IV regression method. When the signal is red, the estimated coefficients of prior odds and likelihood ratio are close to one.²² All interaction terms are not significant. Subjects in my study slightly exhibit a bias of base-rate neglect and under-inference, but these belief updating biases are not the drive for expert and quack choices. I also estimate these coefficients for the reported posteriors after the white signal. Subjects on average are being Bayesian when the test is an expert, but demonstrate the bias of over-inference when the test is a quack. Instead of having different updating abilities for red and white signal, the distinctive bias patterns are more likely to ascribe to the reverse causality between posteriors after white signal and how quacks are defined. To better identify the effect of priors and tests, I also split the sample and estimated two coefficients separately.²³ The results are in columns (9)–(12). All results are still valid.

The coefficients of Grether regressions provide a convenient illustration of subjects' probability weighting functions in the shape specified in Gonzalez and Wu (1999). The curvature parameter is the same as the coefficient $\hat{\beta}_2$, and the elevation parameter is $(\mu/(1-\mu))^{\hat{\beta}_1-\hat{\beta}_2}$.²⁴ The paramount evidence of base-rate neglect and under-inference bias in literature often suggests the relationship between the stated posteriors and the Bayesian ones is an inverse S-shaped curve. This is documented in Enke and Graeber (2019). Figure 9 in Appendix C.1 depicts the estimated probability weighting curves in my experiment. The curvature and elevation parameters are calculated based on coefficients in columns (5) and (9) of Table 6. Since my subjects are generally Bayesian, their stated posterior beliefs for both expert and quack tests are linear with respect to Bayesian posteriors. When the prior is large, they are slightly under-weighting posterior probabilities

²²These estimates are much larger than the ones in the literature. Benjamin (2019) meta-analyzed results of belief updating biases based on posteriors elicited from Grether (1980)'s bookbag-and-poker-chip experiments. The estimated coefficient $\hat{\beta}_1$ ranges from 0.43 (for all fourteen papers) to 0.61 (for sub-sample of six papers with incentivized experiments), and the coefficient $\hat{\beta}_2$ ranges from 0.20 to 0.38. Enke and Graeber (2019) ran a similar belief updating experiment and found the coefficient is 0.52 for prior odds and 0.44 for likelihood ratio. Ambuehl and Li (2018) estimated $\hat{\beta}_2$ at the individual level and found the mean is 0.91 for 143 subjects. I also run Grether regressions for each one of 58 subjects in my experiment. The mean is 0.91 for $\hat{\beta}_1$ and 0.83 for $\hat{\beta}_2$. (see Appendix C.1 for details.)

²³I first run Grether regressions for the reported posteriors of decision problems in P1. Their prior is one half, making the term regarding prior odds vanishes and providing an estimate of β_2 . Then I estimate β_1 based on answers for the rest decision problems in P2-P7. The term replacing likelihood ratio is the fitted value from the first stage regression.

²⁴The probability weighting curve of belief posteriors can be very different from the ones used in evaluating lotteries as in Tversky and Kahneman (1979) and Tversky and Kahneman (1992). The ones for lotteries often describe how people perceive the explicitly given probabilities. The one I considered for posteriors incorporates both the perception and belief updating processes.

for quack tests.

I also run these regressions for each subject. The results are in Appendix C.1. Table 12 provides a summary of the estimation results. Moreover, I divide subjects into two groups, one has quack choices above the median frequency, and the other half has more expert choices. Figure 10 compares their distributions of each estimated coefficient. The group with more expert choices is slightly closer to Bayesian updating than the other group. In general, subjects are Bayesian, and two groups of subjects do not exhibit much difference in belief updating biases.

5.1.2 Sub-optimal bet choices

Given their posteriors of the state, are subjects choosing the optimal bet? The failure of best-responding to their own beliefs may also contribute to quack choices. Costa-Gomes and Weizsäcker (2008) provide evidence for such failures in strategic games. Subjects in their experiment play two-person games and state their beliefs about what their opponents will do. They find players' strategy is not consistent with their stated beliefs for more than half of the games. In my experiment, subjects face individual decision-making problems. Their beliefs and bets are both on the true state of the world, and it is straightforward for them to infer optimal bets from beliefs. Indeed, subjects' bet choices in auxiliary tasks are best responding to their reported posteriors.

Table 7 reports the distribution of subjects' bet choices, clustered for expert and quack tests and different signals. When the signal is red, subjects recognize that the optimal bet is on state L regardless of the chosen test. The rate is 95% under quack and 92% under expert test. The bet choices are largely consistent with their reported beliefs and the corresponding Bayesian beliefs. When the signal is white, subjects predominantly bet state L under quacks (71%) and state R under experts (92%). This finding confirms the failure in distinguishing experts and quacks. It also suggests that people did not realize that a test is useless if it leads to the same action for both signals. However, subjects' bet choices are still highly consistent with their reported beliefs and the Bayesian posteriors, implying the bias in best-responding does not drive quack choices. Table 13 in Appendix C.2 further reports the number of belief-inconsistent bet choices for both quack and expert tests. Overall, only 3% of bets are strictly inconsistent with the reported and the Bayesian posteriors, and those made under quack and expert tests each take around 1.5%.

		Bet L	Indifferent	Bet R	
Quack	red	empirical	271	—	15
		under reported belief	256	23	7
		under Bayesian belief	262	24	0
	white	empirical	202	—	84
		under reported belief	178	77	31
		under Bayesian belief	203	83	0
Expert	red	empirical	483	—	43
		under reported belief	473	3	50
		under Bayesian belief	482	0	44
	white	empirical	42	—	484
		under reported belief	54	8	464
		under Bayesian belief	44	0	482

Table 7: Distributions of empirical bet choices and those consistent with the reported and Bayesian posterior beliefs

I also consider two alternative definitions of experts and quacks. One is based on subjects’ reported posteriors, and the other is on subjects’ bet choices. A test is a “belief quack” (or “bet quack”) if the expected winning probability of having the test is the same as the prior according to the DM’s reported beliefs (or bet choices). Compare to the rational DM who updates beliefs accurately and bets optimally, each definition relaxes an aspect of rationality with subjects’ own evaluations of the chosen test. The belief-based definition admits subjective inference in the process of evaluating tests, and the action-based definition focuses on the consequences of choosing tests. Figure 6 provides the histogram of quacks choices under each definition. In summary, frequencies of quacks are robust under various definitions, confirming that neither the belief updating bias nor the best-responding bias explains quack choices.

5.1.3 Intrinsic preferences over test characteristics

I continue to examine whether intrinsic preferences play a role in quack choices. If subjects care about a specific attribute, and tests on quack segments are more likely to have the attribute than those on expert segments, many test choices will be quacks. For example, if a DM has a strong preference for symmetric accuracies, all of her test choices are quacks since the default symmetric tests always induce the same winning probability as the prior. In the literature, intrinsic preferences often capture a taste for skewness. Masatlioglu et al. (2017) find people prefer pos-

Figure 6: The histogram of quack choices under alternative definitions.

itively skewed test²⁵ in an experiment with non-instrumental information. Their definitions of skewness are not applicable in my setting. With the instrumentally valuable information, subjects choose bet for each possible signal realizations, and such action contingency blends the desired and undesired outcomes. In other words, there is no high or low outcome in my experiment because both bets on state L and R have chances to win a same prize. Moreover, I elicit preferences over tests through pairs of steep and flat budgets. Even though all priors favor state L , these budget pairs produce similar opportunities to resolve state L and R .

I consider asymmetry measures based on the test (p, q) itself and its induced posterior distribution (μ_r, μ_l) . The test-specific measures include the absolute difference between two accuracy levels $|p - q|$ and its distance to the default symmetric test $\|(p, q) - \text{pivot}\|$. The posterior-specific asymmetry is described by the unconditional probability of red signal. This is due to the martingale property of belief updating $\mu_l \mathbb{P}(\text{red}) + \mu_r (1 - \mathbb{P}(\text{red})) = \mu$. Since people also care about how asymmetric a test is relative to alternative ones, I consider a relative version for each asymmetry measure: the accuracy ratio q/p , the slope $(q - \text{pivot})/(\text{pivot} - p)$, and the relative belief updating ratio $(\mu_l - \mu)/(\mu - \mu_r)$.²⁶

²⁵In their setting, a test is positively skewed if it resolves more uncertainty about the high outcome than about the low outcome.

²⁶Bordalo, Gennaioli, and Shleifer (2012)'s salience theory provides explanations for the preference over both absolute and relative skewness for risk lotteries. Studies on prudence (see Trautmann and van de Kuilen (2018) for a survey) show that people prefer positively skewed lotteries. Dertwinkel-Kalt and Köster (2019) provides experimental evidence for the preference over relative

Table 8 summarizes six asymmetry measures. They vary a lot. Some of them like the accuracy ratio and the relative belief updating ratio are close to the symmetric benchmark of one. Other measures document subjects' preferences over asymmetries. For instance, subjects choose color compositions generating slightly more red balls than white balls for Box A. Yet, most measures are comparable between expert and quack tests. Table 14 in Appendix C.2 reports Probit regression results of test choices on each of the asymmetry measure, and none of them predict quack choices. Taken together, I find people exhibit similar preferences for variously defined asymmetry measures. Therefore, intrinsic preferences over test characteristics do not justify quack choices.

		mean	sd	pt5	pt25	pt50	pt75	pt95
$ p - q $	quack	0.51	0.33	0.00	0.23	0.57	0.82	0.88
	expert	0.47	0.28	0.00	0.23	0.42	0.75	0.90
$\ ((p, q) - \text{pivot})\ $	quack	0.41	0.28	0.00	0.18	0.45	0.69	0.76
	expert	0.36	0.20	0.00	0.20	0.34	0.53	0.67
$\mathbb{P}(\text{red})$	quack	0.65	0.24	0.17	0.49	0.64	0.89	0.92
	expert	0.62	0.25	0.24	0.43	0.55	0.90	0.97
q/p	quack	0.94	1.13	0.00	0.06	0.70	1.44	3.57
	expert	1.02	0.72	0.10	0.25	1.12	1.54	2.50
$(q - \text{pivot})/(\text{pivot} - p)$	quack	3.54	1.93	0.88	1.50	4.00	6.00	6.00
	expert	3.09	1.73	0.88	2.00	2.50	4.00	6.00
$(\mu_l - \mu)/(\mu - \mu_r)$	quack	1.01	1.43	0.09	0.13	0.56	1.05	4.95
	expert	0.94	0.87	0.03	0.11	0.82	1.31	3.17

Table 8: Summary of asymmetry measures of quack and expert tests. The top six rows are based on absolute measures of asymmetry, and the bottom six rows are on relative measures.

5.2 Explained mechanisms: contingent reasoning and decision rules

This section investigates the remaining channel for quack choices: the failure of contingent reasoning. It is an inference bias occurred when evaluating the usefulness of a test, and it is unobservable. I study people's reasoning bias based on their descriptions on how they chose color compositions.

skewness for choices under risk.

Table 15 in Appendix C.3 lists subjects' comments on how they reason the coloring tasks in the experiment.²⁷ Three decision rules are popular among subjects. The first one is to choose tests whose accuracies are either 0% or 100%, therefore, subjects can resolve the uncertainty about the state for one of the signals. The second rule is to make the coloring of box L and R as different as possible. This rule is intuitive to subjects when they move sliders and observe the dynamic changes of two boxes. The third one is to maximize the chance of one signal so that subjects are more certain about which one of two bets counts.²⁸ I refer to these reasoning processes as *entropy-reducing*, *evidence-separating*, and *signal-separating* rules.

All three decision rules favor tests on the borders of (p, q) space. I illustrate this point through coloring representations of border tests in Table 9. Each entry plots a simplified version of how box L and R and the induced posteriors look like under the considered border test. Tests on the top-left border allocate as many as white balls for box R until it is full, bringing about a certainty of state L after a red signal, a noticeable difference between two boxes in their coloring, and a highest chance to receive a white signal. These decision rules also justify the choices of tests on the bottom-right border. However, I construct the decision problems with paired budgets such that none of the decision rules guarantees expert (or quack) choices. Both types of border tests can be experts or quacks, depending on the budget. When it is steep, accuracy q is relatively cheaper than p , making the top test $(1/2, 1)$ the most useful expert and the bottom test $(3/4, 0)$ a quack. The opposite holds for flat budgets. The key to distinguish the expert and the quack between two border tests still hinges on whether the test induces a pooling or separating bet choices. In fact, all decision rules acknowledge the optimal expert tests if subjects reason contingently.

My classification of decision rules are different from ones considered in the literature due to the unique approach to construct the choice set of tests. For example, in Charness et al. (2018) and Montanari and Nunnari (2019)'s experiment, subjects choose one from two test options, one biases towards the state favored by the prior, and the other one biases against it. Charness et al. (2018) consider the symmetric case where the prior-confirming test is $(1, \lambda)$, and the prior-contradicting test is

²⁷I did not report uninformative comments or those do not describe decision processes such as "I calculated probabilities" and "I made a guess".

²⁸Typical comments for these decision rules are: (1) "I made sure that wherever I could, there was an option that red or white would 100% be label R or L" from the subject with ID 59; (2) "The colour choices are based on the difference in red and white between L and R, you make the gap as big as possible so its easier to choose L or R from red and white. The bet is then based on the ratio between the gaps." from ID 8; and (3) "Try to favor one colour, increasing the chances for one colour to have a high change to belong to one of the boxes" from ID 43.

Table 9: An illustration of border tests and their induced posterior distributions for the steep and flat budget in P3. The expert test on the top-left border of the steep budget shares the same value as the one on the bottom-right border of the flat budget.

$(\lambda, 1)$. Montanari and Nunnari (2019) consider the asymmetric case where one is $(1, \lambda)$, and the other one is $(1 - \lambda, 1)$. Both cases coincide with two border tests of the flat budget in my setting. The top-left test is prior-contradicting, and the bottom-right one is prior-confirming. In addition, each one of them corresponds to a comparable border test on the steep budget. For instance, the accuracies of two expert tests are carefully designed to generate the same extent of usefulness for betting decisions. Such constructions allow for a new identification for the relationship between test choices and decision rules.

Since all decision rules rationalize border tests, I quantify each one of them by

an attribute of border tests. Each considered attribute reflects how the corresponding rule favors border tests. First, I measure the decision rule that aims to reduce overall uncertainty by the decrease of entropy from the prior to the induced posterior. It is based on Shannon (1948)'s entropy concept for the uncertainty inherent in a random variable, and further developed in Cabrales, Gossner, and Serrano (2013) for the uncertainty induced by an information structure.²⁹ I measure the evidence-separating rule by the coloring differences between two boxes. More specifically, it equals to $|p - (1 - q)|$, the absolute gap between the proportion of red (or white) balls for each box given test (p, q) . The signal-separating rule is calibrated by the unconditional probability of the dominating signal, which is $\mathbb{P}(\text{red})$ for top-left tests and $\mathbb{P}(\text{white})$ for bottom-right tests.

I examine how these rule-specific measures affect subjects' test choices through reduced-form Probit regressions. Table 10 reports the results. Columns (1)–(3) show that measures for each decision rule are highly predictive for expert versus quack choices.³⁰ The chosen test is more likely to be a quack if the top test on the same budget resolves more uncertainties, or both the top and bottom tests generate larger differences in the coloring between two boxes. A bottom test allocating more white balls to Box *A* predicts a higher chance of choosing an expert test. It is very likely that three decision rules influence quack (or expert) choices via the indirect channel of influencing choices on the top or bottom segments of budgets (see regression in column (4)). I regress a dummy variable for tests on the top segments over the measures for each rule in columns (5)–(7). Subjects' choices on the top segment are significantly affected by entropy-reducing and evidence-separating rules, but not signal-separating rule.³¹

I predict the rates of choosing quacks if subjects use entropy-reducing or evidence-separating rules to choose choices on top segments. This is possible due to my paired construction of budgets under which all choices on top segments are experts when budgets are steep, and they are quacks when budgets are flat. Figure 7 compares the actual quack rates with the predicted ones across budgets in P2-P7.

²⁹Here is a formal calculation of entropy reduction. Denote the Shannon entropy of an arbitrary belief distribution as $H(\mu') = -(\mu' \log_2(\mu') + (1 - \mu') \log_2(1 - \mu'))$, where μ' is belief (prior or posterior) over state L . For a test (p, q) , its entropy is an expectation of $H(\mu_s(p, q; \mu))$, weighted by the unconditional probability of each signal. The expected decrease of entropy from the prior to the posterior induced by (p, q) is $\Delta H(p, q; \mu) = H(\mu) - \sum_s H(\mu_s(p, q; \mu))\mathbb{P}(s)$.

³⁰The coefficients of top and bottom attributes are jointly significant in each one of the regressions under χ^2 -test. p-values are 0.044 for entropy-reducing measures, 0.000 for both evidence-separating and signal-separating measures.

³¹Joint hypotheses tests on the coefficients of top and bottom attributes show that p-values are 0.032 and 0.015 respectively for the entropy-reducing and evidence-separating rule. p-value is 0.619 for attributes measuring the signal-separating rule.

	<i>Dependent: D(expert choice)</i>				<i>Dependent: D(top choice)</i>		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
Constant	-1.83 (2.36)	-45.74** (8.43)	-3.46 (6.13)	0.13* (0.06)	-5.69* (2.35)	-22.66** (7.82)	0.56 (5.17)
Slope	0.84 (0.52)	10.60** (1.91)	-1.12 (1.15)		1.40** (0.51)	5.44** (1.75)	-0.11 (0.97)
Size	-1.33 (0.72)	-14.88** (2.66)	0.97 (1.51)		-2.27** (0.71)	-7.81** (2.44)	-0.19 (1.27)
Quack chance	-3.72** (0.52)	-3.52** (0.38)	-2.72** (0.69)		-1.59** (0.48)	-1.00** (0.30)	-1.18* (0.58)
Steep	0.89* (0.41)	2.48** (0.47)	0.85** (0.29)		1.34** (0.41)	1.71** (0.45)	1.01** (0.29)
Pivot point	9.32 (4.99)	104.96** (18.57)	7.74 (11.79)		13.53** (4.88)	50.36** (17.05)	-0.98 (9.85)
D(Top choice)				0.44** (0.10)			
Top: $\Delta(\text{entropy})$	-5.28* (2.22)				-4.50* (2.10)		
Bottom: $\Delta(\text{entropy})$	-3.44 (2.19)				-4.38* (2.17)		
Top: $ p + q - 1 $		-25.89** (4.54)				-11.03** (4.10)	
Bottom: $ p + q - 1 $		-13.58** (2.87)				-7.42** (2.60)	
Top: $\mathbb{P}(\text{red})$			-2.30 (3.88)				2.03 (3.20)
Bottom: $\mathbb{P}(\text{white})$			12.55** (2.89)				2.27 (2.66)
Observations	696	696	696	696	696	696	696
<i>Note:</i>	p<0.1; *p<0.05; **p<0.01						

Table 10: Probit regression results for three heuristics

Both decision rules predict distributions of quacks similar to the actual one. On average, the predicted quack rates are slightly higher, but none of them are significantly different from the actual quack rate under t -test and Wilcoxon rank sum test. This finding implies that quack choices are simply by-products of choices under simple decision rules. Furthermore, it confirms the universal failures of contingent reasoning. When facing the interaction between test choices and bet choices, people fail to reason the distinction between useful and useless tests, and they use simple decision rules aiming to reduce overall uncertainties or differentiate evidence structures.

Figure 7: The histogram of predicted quack choice rate for budgets in P2-P7.

Notice that these decision rules are not substitutes to contingent reasoning. It is not the case that subjects turn to simple decision rules because they find it difficult to reason contingently. For example, under the entropy-reducing rule, a DM cares about how much the induced posterior distributions resolve the overall uncertainties about the state. However, such consideration does not internalize the contingent reasoning in how expert and quack tests affect the optimal actions in different ways. Similarly, neither evidence-separating nor signal-separating rule considers the influence of tests on actions. In other words, contingent reasoning is not exclusive to decision rules. A subject who reasons contingently and employs each one of the rules will choose the optimal test. Since these rules favor the salient tests on the border, many subjects either choose the most useful experts or the most distant quacks.

Additional analyses on post-experiment questionnaires show that quack choices are correlated with individual cognitive abilities. Table 16 in Appendix C.4 reports regression results of subjects' quack choice rate over demographic variables, self-assessed attitudes, and cognitive scores. Subjects with higher CRT scores are choosing less quacks, while the other two psychometric measures are not significant. Self-reported attitudes include risk aversion and having strong opinions predict more quack choices. Surprisingly, subjects who self-reported to be good at figuring out useful clues are also making more quack choices. The attitudes determining quack choices are not the same as the ones for Bayesian updating. I run similar regressions for individual measures of belief updating bias in Table 17. The CRT score is still significant. In addition, being male and the self-reported ability to have different perspectives predict a lower updating bias.³²

6 Discussion and implication

In my setting, individuals choose tests to reduce risks over two payoff relevant states. I characterize the state-outcome correspondence by two bets having symmetric outcomes. Under this construction, individuals' preferences over outcomes are irrelevant to their decisions of tests. The outcome π can be non-monetary. All subjects compare their beliefs with the fixed threshold of one half. One implication is that my setup is immune to individuals' utility-specific risk attitudes. The threshold has already encapsulated different shapes of utility functions over outcomes.³³ When the prizes for two states are not symmetric, for instance, the case of choosing medical tests, we can elicit each individual's threshold beforehand.³⁴ All theoretical analyses and the experiment remain valid to study people's choices of tests and reasoning biases.

The contingent reasoning bias is not restricted to a setting with binary signals or binary states.³⁵ For decision problems with non-binary signals, the DM up-

³²In unreported tables, CRT score and perspective ability are still significant when the measures for individual updating biases are coefficients estimated from Grether regressions.

³³Individuals' probability-specific risk attitudes are often reflected by different shapes of probability weighting functions. When evaluating tests, people's reported posterior probabilities incorporate how they inference signals and how they perceive probabilities. Therefore, people's probability-specific risk attitudes and inference biases are indistinguishable from each other. I generically refer to the deviation from the Bayesian posteriors as belief-updating biases.

³⁴A DM's decision threshold is her belief over state L that makes her indifferent between bets on state L and R . We can easily elicit the threshold by matching the probability of a bet with the high prize with the option of receiving the low prize for sure.

³⁵Notice all discussions of states and signals admit standard assumptions in the literature. The

dates beliefs for each signal and evaluates tests based on signal-contingent winning probabilities. When there are more than two states, the DM chooses bets according to multiple thresholds, each corresponding to an indifference between two bets. All thresholds partition the DM's belief space into different regions, and beliefs in each region support one particular bet being optimal.³⁶ None of the extensions fundamentally changes the evaluation process of tests. A test is an expert when it induces posteriors spreading at different belief partitions, and it is a quack if it induces posteriors supporting the same bet as in prior.

The supply side of tests may also submit to the contingent reasoning bias. Many studies in contract theory and mechanism design are related to the optimal disclosure of information from an ex ante perspective. For instance, Lizzeri (1999), Eső and Szentes (2007a), Eső and Szentes (2007b), and Li and Shi (2017) consider the case where a seller knows customers' match-value of a good and commits to a disclosure rule (before knowing the type of the customer) and a price policy to maximize revenues (or screen customers). Bergemann, Bonatti, and Smolin (2018) studies the sales of ex ante information.³⁷ A data seller owns a database regarding the states and offers data buyers different versions of statistical experiments (tests) before the realization of the true state. A seller who cannot anticipate how different tests influence customers' decisions may not be able to design the optimal contract or information products. On the other hand, a seller may also take advantage of buyers' reasoning bias and obfuscate them with quack tests on purpose. Our findings are relevant to policy regulations on such markets.

The contingent reasoning principle also applies to a strategic setting. A sender chooses a test, and a receiver learns a realization of the signal and then take action. Their interests are not aligned, motivating the sender to choose particular tests to serve his ends. This setting relates to an extensive literature on information design. For example, Myerson (1991) analyzes the value of communication in sender-receiver games and illustrates how a mediator improves information transmission via an appropriately chosen test. A sender in Kamenica and Gentzkow (2011)'s Bayesian persuasion model commits to an information structure to persuade a receiver to choose the action the sender prefers as likely as possible.³⁸ More discus-

state space is finite. The action space of bets is the same as the state space. The size of the signal space is not smaller than that of the state space.

³⁶Formal proofs are out of the scope of this paper. Interested readers are referred to Kamenica (2019)'s discussion of the concavification approach for the value function of information structures and Lara and Gossner (2020)'s convex analyses for the duality between payoffs and posteriors.

³⁷Bergemann and Bonatti (2019) provides a recent review on the market for both ex ante and ex post information.

³⁸Kamenica (2019) provides a recent survey on Bayesian persuasion models. A review of the

sions about different mechanisms of information design and their connections can be found in Bergemann and Morris (2019). My findings suggest an important yet often neglected reasoning requirement for this strand of literature. The reasoning biases from either the sender or the receiver side have concrete implications for both the theoretical validity and the empirical implementation of these mechanisms.

7 Conclusion

This paper provides a unified framework of expert and quack tests and studies how people choose and evaluate them. Using a budget experiment, I document the failure in distinguishing experts and quacks and examine underlying mechanisms. People frequently select quacks even though many decision-enhancing expert tests are also in their choice set. This finding is not explained by belief-updating bias, sub-optimal action choices, or intrinsic preferences over test characteristics. People choose quacks because of the failure of contingent reasoning in information processing.

This reasoning bias has profound consequences for many decision problems. It leads to demand (or supply) for inferior information sources or obfuscating disclosure policies at the beginning of decision-making. Once a DM chooses a quack test, all her efforts in correcting cognitive biases and choice mistakes will be in vain. However, the cost of de-biasing can be meager. As long as the DM realizes the interaction between tests and their influences on decision problems, she will choose optimally even under simple decision rules. This paper also suggests that de-biasing interventions targeted to reasoning processes may be more beneficial than those targeted to belief or action biases. How to educate people to reason contingently is worth future study.

empirical work on persuasion can be found in DellaVigna and Gentzkow (2010).

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Appendices

A Proofs

Proposition 1. *An admissible test induces a Bayesian posterior spread such that observing signal l (or r) increases the posterior of the state L (or R) relative to the prior, and vice versa. Mathematically, for any prior μ , a test $(p, q) \in \mathcal{T} \iff \mu_r^{Bayes}(p, q; \mu) \leq \mu \leq \mu_l^{Bayes}(p, q; \mu)$.*

Proof. Given a prior $\mu \in [1/2, 1)$ and an arbitrary test (p, q) , the Bayesian posteriors after signal l and r are

$$\mu_l^{Bayes} = \frac{p\mu}{p\mu + (1-\mu)(1-q)} \quad \text{and} \quad \mu_r^{Bayes} = \frac{(1-p)\mu}{(1-p)\mu + q(1-\mu)}.$$

The inequality $\mu_l^{Bayes} \geq \mu$ holds if and only if $p + q \geq 1$, implying the test is admissible. Analogously, the inequality $\mu_r^{Bayes} \leq \mu$ is also equivalent to the admissible condition. \square

Proposition 2. *Given a rational DM and a prior μ , an admissible test (p, q) is an expert (a quack) if and only if the condition $(1-p)\mu - q(1-\mu) < 0$ is (not) satisfied. The value of an expert test is $v^{Bayes}(p, q; \mu) = p\mu + q(1-\mu)$, and the value of a quack test is μ .*

Proof. In my setting, a test is an expert for a rational DM if and only if the Bayesian posterior belief after signal r is smaller than one half. Solving $\mu_r^{Bayes} < 1/2$ yields the inequality

$$(1-p)\mu - q(1-\mu) < 0.$$

With the inequality $\mu_r^{Bayes} < 1/2$, the rational DM's ex-ante winning probability is

$$\begin{aligned} v^{Bayes}(p, q; \mu) &= \mu_l^{Bayes} \mathbb{P}(s = l) + (1 - \mu_r^{Bayes}) \mathbb{P}(s = r) \\ &= \mathbb{P}(l | L) \mathbb{P}(L) + \mathbb{P}(r | R) \mathbb{P}(R) \\ &= p\mu + q(1 - \mu). \end{aligned}$$

On the contrary, a test is a quack for a rational DM if and only if $\mu_r^{Bayes} \geq 1/2$. With this inequality, the value of the test is

$$\begin{aligned} v^{Bayes}(p, q; \mu) &= \mu_l^{Bayes} \mathbb{P}(s = l) + \mu_r^{Bayes} \mathbb{P}(s = r) \\ &= \mathbb{E}_s \mu_s^{Bayes} \\ &= \mu. \quad (\text{iterated law of expectations}) \end{aligned}$$

B More details on the experimental design

Figure 8: Fourteen linear budgets for the experiment. The solid dots on each budget indicate the optimal choice of the test. Two dotted lines in the right panel are the indifference curves for budget pair P6 and P7 respectively.

Table 11: Constructing Box L and R for each budget. $N(L)$ is the number of balls in Box L . $\text{Step}(L)$ is the precision of Box L 's slider, indicating the minimum numbers of balls can be colored. All probabilities are discretized based on these natural frequencies.

No.	(Prior, Pivot)	Budget	$N(L)$	$N(R)$	$\text{Step}(L)$	$\text{Step}(R)$
P1(S)	(1/2, 1/2)	$2p + q = 3/2$	50	50	1	2
P1(F)	(1/2, 1/2)	$p/2 + q = 3/4$	50	50	2	1
P2(S)	(3/5, 3/5)	$2p + q = 9/5$	135	90	3	4
P2(F)	(3/5, 3/5)	$5p/4 + q = 27/20$	150	100	6	5
P3(S)	(3/5, 3/5)	$4p + q = 3$	135	90	3	8
P3(F)	(3/5, 3/5)	$7p/8 + q = 9/8$	150	100	12	7
P4(S)	(2/3, 2/3)	$4p + q = 10/3$	120	60	2	4
P4(F)	(2/3, 2/3)	$3p/2 + q = 5/3$	120	60	4	3
P5(S)	(3/4, 3/4)	$6p + q = 21/4$	120	40	2	4
P5(F)	(3/4, 3/4)	$5p/2 + q = 21/8$	120	40	6	5
P6(S)	(3/5, 3/4)	$6p + q = 21/4$	60	40	1	4
P6(F)	(3/5, 3/4)	$5p/2 + q = 21/8$	120	80	3	5
P7(S)	(2/3, 3/4)	$6p + q = 21/4$	60	40	1	3
P7(F)	(2/3, 3/4)	$5p/2 + q = 21/8$	120	60	4	5

C Additional analyses

C.1 Additional analyses on belief updating bias

Figure 9: Probability weighting functions estimated from the coefficients in Grether regressions.

Table 12: Summary of belief updating regression results at the individual level. The coefficients are for Bayesian posteriors ($\hat{\alpha}_1$) in OLS regression, log prior odds ($\hat{\beta}_1$) and log likelihood ratio ($\hat{\beta}_2$) in Grether regression. The quantile a is denoted as pta .

		mean	sd	pt5	pt25	pt50	pt75	pt95
pool	Bayes posterior	0.94	0.15	0.65	0.91	0.99	1.00	1.06
red	Bayes posterior	0.87	0.24	0.34	0.80	0.98	1.00	1.03
white	Bayes posterior	0.89	0.41	0.31	0.94	1.00	1.00	1.09
pool	ln(prior odds)	0.61	0.34	0.09	0.40	0.58	0.82	1.18
	ln(likelihood ratio)	1.06	0.32	0.46	1.04	1.15	1.21	1.31
red	ln(prior odds)	0.91	0.90	-0.04	0.56	0.93	1.05	2.16
	ln(likelihood ratio)	0.83	0.53	-0.11	0.85	0.99	1.02	1.08
white	ln(prior odds)	0.59	1.24	-1.44	0.39	0.83	1.20	1.69
	ln(likelihood ratio)	1.16	0.68	0.47	1.17	1.33	1.39	1.49

Figure 10: The mean and 95% confidence intervals of the estimated coefficients in OLS regression for Bayesian posteriors and Grether regression for likelihood ratio and prior odds. The coefficients are based on subjects' posteriors after the red signal.

C.2 Additional analyses on sub-optimal bet choices and test characteristics

Table 13: Counts of bet choices that are strictly inconsistent with the reported beliefs and the Bayesian beliefs

		Under reported belief		Under Bayesian belief	
		quack	expert	quack	expert
Red	incorrectly bet R	3	2	6	2
	incorrectly bet L	4	9	0	3
White	incorrectly bet R	13	15	29	7
	incorrectly bet L	6	3	0	5
Total		26	29	35	17

Table 14: Probit regressions of quack choices on different measures of test asymmetries. The control variables include the random quack chance for each budget and the interaction point of each pair of budgets.

	Dependent variable: dummy for quack choices					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Constant	-2.76** (0.65)	-2.78** (0.64)	-2.59** (0.63)	-2.45** (0.66)	-3.36** (0.90)	-2.88** (0.69)
Quack chance	2.54** (0.26)	2.52** (0.26)	2.52** (0.26)	2.52** (0.26)	2.77** (0.33)	2.56** (0.26)
Pivot point	1.55 (0.84)	1.49 (0.83)	1.24 (0.85)	1.31 (0.86)	2.66* (1.30)	1.78* (0.88)
$ p - q $	0.18 (0.17)					
$\ (p, q) - \text{pivot}\ $		0.43 (0.22)				
$\mathbb{P}(\text{red})$			0.24 (0.21)			
q/p				-0.04 (0.06)		
$(q - \text{pivot})/(\text{pivot} - p)$					-0.05 (0.04)	
$(\mu_l - \mu)/(\mu - \mu_r)$						0.05 (0.05)
Observations	696	696	696	696	696	696
Note:	·p<0.1; *p<0.05; **p<0.01					

C.3 Individual comments and decision rules

Table 15: Individual quack choice rates, Bayesian updating coefficients, and comments

ID	Quack	$1 - \hat{\alpha}_1$	Comments
4	0.29	0.04	while betting white gives R a small advantage, it also nearly guarantees an L on a red ball, making any choice valid
7	0.21	0.44	I did it where I would have a much better chance at getting a certain number and percentage to chose from
8	0.43	0.11	The colour choices are based on the difference in red and white between L and R, you make the gap as big as possible so its easier to choose L or R from red and white. The bet is then based on the ratio between the gaps.
10	0.29	-0.00	Made the easiest to calculate, for most secure bets.
11	0.29	0.00	If there is only one kind of a color, for ex, all white are L (like in this case), one of the chances is eliminated, as there is no possible bet to do. If the ball is white, it is 100% sure L, so we only bet once in two tries (kind of).
13	0.21	-0.00	My strategy for each round was to try and determine what selection of colors would give the clearest option for the largest number of balls. In the last round, 14, I isolated 70 red balls on the left side and left no red balls on the right side, that way if a ball was red, it was guaranteed to be a left-side ball. This means that I have certainty on a little more than a third of the balls, and then determining if the ball was left or right when the ball was white was closer to a coin flip. I determined my bet choices by simply dividing the number of balls on one side of a color by the total number of balls of that color.
16	0.36	0.00	i just tried to find the optimal split so that the coloured balls would have the most value
18	0.29	0.02	I tried to make the biggest difference in number of coloured and non-coloured balls
20	0.36	0.00	I was trying to make 100% chance in one of the colours, and count the other probability.
21	0.29	0.24	I tried, if possible, to have a color appear only in one box so as to make sure that it will 100% be in that box. If that wasn't possible, I tried to gather as much of it in one box so as to minimize/maximize the chances.
22	0.50	0.21	I tried to make the ratios of white in box L and R as great as possible

Individual quack choice rates, Bayesian updating coefficients, and comments (cnt)

ID	Quack	$1 - \hat{\alpha}_1$	Comments
23	0.29	0.24	Initially, I observe which of the two colours has the safest ratio, in this case I identified RED L as the safest colour to place my bet on. Secondly, I see that the two whites are now slightly higher than a 50/50 chance, so I naturally get on the WHITE R as the odds are ever-so-slightly in my favour, meanwhile I am certain to win the bet on the red colours.
24	0.50	0.004	Tried to do it with an excel spreadsheet but ended up just using basic math knowledge.
26	0.29	-0.00	I choose the colour trying to have the balls in one of the boxes all of the same colour, like all white balls. When this was possible I was able to bet that in that box I had 0% possibilities to finds a red ball. In the other cases I just calculated the percentage mathematically
27	0.29	0.01	I moved the sliders until I thought that the differences in the numbers of white and red balls in box R and L were far enough apart to make a significant difference in statistics (I was just eyeballing it). Once I was satisfied, I confirmed the selection and then worked out the probabilities by taking the number of coloured balls in one box and dividing by the total number of coloured balls to work out the chance of it occurring. E.g. Red L / Red L + Red R = 0.71 so if the ball is red I know there is a 71% chance of it being red. I did this all the time so my bets where always statistically likely to be right (even if just by a little)
28	0.36	0.01	calculated how likely it was to get left or right for both red and white balls and calculated the chance of getting a red or white ball. Did this for both the extremes of colour choices and compared
29	0.43	0.15	i tried making the colours based on which had the furthest overall chances from 50/50 in both categories at the same time, then (mostly) bet on those with higher chances
30	0.21	0.02	tried to make it so only one box had one colour so it would definitely come from that box
35	0.29	0.15	I looked at the ratio between red and white in each box, and make them different
36	0.21	0.04	Rough estimation of possibilities for different outcomes (considering the amount of colored balls) then choosing the one that has the most chance of winning
37	0.29	0.28	Simply Getting as many red balls as possible for L
39	0.29	0.02	I tried to balance the colors in the way that should make it easier for me to guess the chance in the bet choices. When betting, I roughly estimated the percentages looking on the number of balls of given color.

Individual quack choice rates, Bayesian updating coefficients, and comments (cnt)

ID	Quack	$1 - \hat{\alpha}_1$	Comments
41	0.14	-0.00	I tried to somewhat increase the difference between the amount of balls between each box
42	0.36	0.69	I tried to pick the colors to make my choice easier. For example if there was no white balls with the label R, then it was easier to make the choice and estimation.
43	0.29	-0.00	Try to favor one colour, increasing the chances for one colour to have a high change to belong to one of the boxes
44	0.36	0.66	My bet obviously hindered on my color choices but when choosing my color choices I just tried to do a variety of outcomes to see how unique I could make each round. I enjoyed testing how moving one slider influences the other so it was a lot of experimenting.
45	0.36	0.05	I just used the highest chance of it being red or white.
51	0.50	-0.00	Went for the safest option, knowing that if it's red I can guarantee that it will be L
56	0.29	0.07	I moved the slider all the way towards whichever side caused the most red balls to be in one of the two boxes and the least red balls to be in the second box (in example 9, moving the slider all the way to the left caused 86 balls in box L and only 2 balls in box R). I predicted if ball A is red, it will have been drawn from box L from the percentage calculation of 86/88 meaning that 98% of the red balls in box A are from box L. If the ball is white, I added the total amount of white balls (72 in example 9) and predicted that the ball would come from whichever box had more white balls remaining. In example 9, box R had more white balls and the percentage was calculated by doing 38 balls from box R divided as a total percentage which was 38/72 or 53%.
58	0.21	0.05	i was trying to make the probabilities of getting at least one of the if-bets right by eliminating most on my chances to guess wrong. For example in round 3, out of 14 whites there was only one chance of the ball being R.
59	0.21	0.02	I made sure that wherever i could, there was an option that red or white would 100% be label R or L
60	0.71	0.52	Based on the ratio in each box and separately. Both have the same number of balls and same ratio of colours.
61	0.21	-0.09	I like to make the colour that i have 100% chance to win if it will be that colour, i do bet from estimated chances
63	0.21	-0.00	I made color choices to make the odds in my favor for both if bets and the bet choices were based on those odds.
64	0.43	0.28	I tried to make both colours have similar amount of balls but also similar numbers of them balls so there is a chance the likelihood would be correct

C.4 Additional analyses on demographics, attitudes, and cognitive abilities

Table 16: Regressions of individual quack choice rate on demographic variables, self-reported psychological attitudes, and cognitive reasoning scores. Regressions in columns (4)–(6) are selected based on Akaike (1998)'s information criterion (AIC).

	Dependent variable: individual rate of quacks					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Constant	0.23 (0.16)	0.20 (0.19)	0.38*** (0.05)	0.14 (0.14)	0.03 (0.12)	0.24 (0.18)
Age	0.004 (0.01)					
Female	0.04 (0.04)					
SAT	0.001 (0.02)					
STEM	0.02 (0.04)					
CRT score			-0.04** (0.02)	-0.03* (0.02)	-0.03** (0.02)	-0.03** (0.02)
Wason score			-0.02 (0.02)			
Logic score			0.02 (0.02)			
Risk		0.04** (0.02)		0.04*** (0.01)	0.04*** (0.01)	0.04** (0.01)
Contingent		-0.04 (0.03)		-0.04 (0.03)		-0.04 (0.03)
Stubborn		0.02 (0.02)		0.03* (0.01)	0.03* (0.01)	0.02 (0.01)
Information		0.06** (0.03)		0.05** (0.02)	0.04* (0.02)	0.06** (0.02)
Perspective		-0.02 (0.03)				-0.02 (0.03)
Analytical		-0.02 (0.02)				
Observations	58	58	58	58	58	58
Adjusted R ²	-0.06	0.15	0.04	0.21	0.19	0.21

Note: *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Table 17: Regressions of individual Bayesian updating bias on demographic variables, self-reported psychological attitudes, and cognitive reasoning scores. Regressions in columns (4)–(6) are selected based on Akaike (1998)’s information criterion (AIC).

	Dependent variable: individual coefficient $1 - \hat{\alpha}_1$					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Constant	0.03 (0.25)	0.11 (0.38)	0.20** (0.09)	0.12 (0.20)	0.22 (0.19)	0.07 (0.21)
Age	-0.004 (0.01)					
Female	0.24*** (0.07)			0.21*** (0.05)	0.21*** (0.05)	0.21*** (0.05)
SAT	0.004 (0.03)					
STEM	0.06 (0.07)					
CRT score			-0.09*** (0.03)	-0.08*** (0.03)	-0.07*** (0.03)	-0.09*** (0.03)
Wason score			-0.04 (0.03)			
Logic score			0.06 (0.04)			0.04 (0.03)
Risk aversion		0.03 (0.03)				
Contingent		0.01 (0.06)				
Stubborn		-0.02 (0.03)				
Information		0.03 (0.05)		0.06 (0.04)		0.05 (0.04)
Perspective		-0.07 (0.05)		-0.10** (0.04)	-0.08** (0.04)	-0.09** (0.04)
Analytical		0.02 (0.05)		0.06 (0.04)	0.07** (0.04)	0.06 (0.04)
Observations	58	58	58	58	58	58
Adjusted R ²	0.17	-0.06	0.13	0.33	0.31	0.33
<i>Note:</i>	*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01					

D Experimental instructions and screenshots

Welcome!

Before we start, here are some remarks:

- Please pay careful attention to the instructions in each of the following pages. They will help you to better understand the experiment and earn more money.
- Please stay focused during the whole session, otherwise we may deny your answers. If you have questions at any time, please send us emails and we will answer it promptly.
- Our study does not involve deception of any kind. We will provide all relevant and truthful information for your decision-making.
- Your choices and answers are anonymous and will be kept confidential.
- For full functionality of this website, please enable JavaScript and use standard web browsers like Chrome or Firefox.

Enter your participant ID here:

Continue

Experiment Overview

About procedure: In today's experiment, you will play **14 rounds** of color and bet tasks. The following pages will show you instructions. Please read them carefully and answer the quiz questions on each page.

About payment: In addition to the base reward of £4.00 for completing the study, you may earn a prize of £10.00 depending on your decisions and on chance. At the end of the experiment, the computer will randomly select **one round to pay**. Each round is equally likely to be selected. **Therefore, your decision in every round might count for your final payoff.**

About duration: The whole experiment will take approximately 40 minutes.

Next

Instructions

Task: bet the label of a ball that will be drawn from Box A

In each round of the task, you will see two boxes — Box L and Box R. They both contain some balls with its own box label. In the example here, Box L contains 75 balls with label "L" and Box R contains 50 balls with label "R".

Later, all balls will be filled into Box A, and the computer will randomly draw one ball from it. We call the chosen ball "Ball A". All balls are equally likely to be drawn. **Before knowing the label of "Ball A", your task is to bet its label to be either "L" or "R".** If your bet is correct, you will get a prize of £10.00; otherwise you will get £0.00.

Here is how your choice question looks like:

I bet that the label of "Ball A" is:

- L R

Please answer the following questions before continuing.

1. For the example with two boxes shown in the above figure, which of the following statements is true?

- A particular ball coming from Box L has the same chance of being drawn from Box A as a particular ball coming from Box R.
- A particular ball coming from Box L has a higher chance of being drawn from Box A than a particular ball coming from Box R.

2. For the example with two boxes shown in the above figure, which bet is more likely to win the prize?

- Bet that the label of "Ball A" is L
- Bet that the label of "Ball A" is R

Submit

Instructions

Task 1: Choose color compositions:

Before putting all balls into Box A, you can choose to color some balls in Box L and Box R to be red. **The coloring process will not affect the label of each ball.**

After choosing the color, all balls in Box L and Box R will be put into Box A, and **you can still bet the label of "Ball A" to win a prize of £10.00.** However, you can make bets separately as if knowing the color of "Ball A".

The coloring task might help you guess the label of "Ball A" better. Why? First, notice that the color composition you choose will determine the likelihood of "Ball A" being red or white. Second, different color compositions for Box L and Box R will help you to infer the label of "Ball A".

How to color balls in Box L and Box R? Below is an example of the choice interface. Play with it to find out!

An example of the choice interface

Task 1. Choose color compositions for Box L and Box R

Box L: 75 Balls **Box R: 50 Balls** **Box A: 125 Balls**

step: 3 step: 4

The current composition of Box A is:

L	L	R	R
45	30	20	30

Click to add all balls to Box A

Show balls Snapshot

Confirm color composition

How to choose color compositions?

There are two sliders below Box L and Box R. You can directly drag them or use arrow keys on your keyboard to change the number of red balls and white balls in each box.

Moving the slider to the right (left) will increase the number of red (white) balls.

Notice that **the increments for red (white) balls in Box L and Box R are linked.** In the example here, if you add three red (white) balls for Box L, four red (white) balls will be automatically added to Box R. The increment steps for each box is shown above the slider.

You can also check how the colored and labeled balls look like in Box A by clicking two buttons below Box A.

Once you are satisfied with your coloring choice, please confirm it by clicking the button "Confirm color composition". After that, you cannot change the color of the balls anymore. In actual tasks, two sliders will disappear.

Task 2. Bet on the label of "Ball A" if knowing its color

If "Ball A" is red, label is ?

I bet that its label is:

LR

I think the likelihood of its label being L vs. R is:

L: 50%R: 50%

If "Ball A" is white, label is ?

I bet that its label is:

LR

I think the likelihood of its label being L vs. R is:

L: 50%R: 50%

Task 2: Choose "if-bets" and provide likelihood estimations

After you confirm the coloring choices for Box L and Box R, all balls will be filled into Box A, and the computer will draw the "Ball A". At the same time, four radio buttons will show up in Task 2.

Suppose you know "Ball A" is red (or white), which bet will you choose? This type of bets is called "if-bet" because it asks you to choose the bet as if knowing the color of "Ball A". Recall that the color compositions you chose in Task 1 determine the color of "Ball A" and might inform you which label is more likely. **Therefore, it can be helpful to check your coloring choices when choosing the bet for both "if-red-bet" and "if-white-bet".**

When will you win the prize of the bet? It depends on your choice, the color, and the label of "Ball A".

- If "Ball A" is red, your bet choice for "if-red-bet" will count. Then, we will compare the label you bet with the actual label of "Ball A". If you bet the label correctly, you will get a prize of £10.00; otherwise, you will get £0.00.
- If "Ball A" is white, the "if-white-bet" will count, and similarly, your payoff depends on whether you bet correctly or not.
- **In summary, the color of "Ball A" determines which one of the two "if-bets" counts and the label of "Ball A" determines whether your bet is correct or not.**

Besides bet choices, please also provide a likelihood estimation for each "if-bet". For example, if you move the slider of the "if-white-bet" to the position 20, you are indicating that if you know "Ball A" is white, you think its label is R with 20% chance and is L with 80% chance.

You can earn an extra bonus up to £1.50 based on your likelihood estimations. How is this bonus calculated? We also asked a mathematician to provide a likelihood estimation for each "if-bet" you face. Once determined which "if-bet" counts, your likelihood estimation for that bet will be compared with the estimation of the mathematician. If the absolute difference between these two estimations is no larger than 5%, you will earn a bonus of £1.50. If the absolute difference is larger than 5%, but no larger than 15%, you will get a bonus of £0.50. Otherwise, if the absolute difference is larger than 15%, you will not have a bonus.

Please answer the following questions before continuing.

1. Which of the following statements is true?

- I can always revise my coloring choices even after clicking the button "Confirm color composition".
- If I add more red balls to Box R, more white balls will be added to Box L.
- I can use the coloring task to increase my chance of choosing the correct bet and my chance of winning the prize.

2. For the choice example shown on this page, suppose Bob decides to color 36 balls in Box L to be red, how many white balls does he keep in Box R? (Move the sliders!)

42

Incorrect Answer

3. For the choice example shown on this page, suppose the current color composition of Box A is (48 red balls and 27 white balls in Box L, 24 red balls and 26 white balls in Box R). If Bob decides to color 12 more red balls in Box R, how many white balls will be removed from Box L?

9

4. Which of the following statements is true?

- The coloring choices I made in Task 1 is irrelevant to the "if-bets" I face in Task 2.
- Suppose I think that the label of "Ball A" is L with 40% chance and is R with 60% chance if it is red, I should move the slider of "if-red-bet" to the position 60.
- Only one of the two "if-bets" will count for my payoff, and it is determined by the label of "Ball A".

5. Suppose Bob's choices for two "if-bets" are: if "Ball A" is red, bet L; if "Ball A" is white, bet R. Suppose "Ball A" is white and has label R, which of the following statements is true?

- The "if-red-bet" counts, and Bob will not win the prize.
- The "if-red-bet" counts, and Bob will win the prize.
- The "if-white-bet" counts, and Bob will not win the prize.
- The "if-white-bet" counts, and Bob will win the prize.

6. Suppose the mathematician estimates that (1) if "Ball A" is red, the chance of "Ball A" having the label R is 60%; and (2) if "Ball A" is white, the chance of "Ball A" having the label R is 40%. Which of the following statements is true?

- If the slider for "if-white-bet" stays within the range [55, 65], the bonus is £1.5.
- If the slider for "if-red-bet" stays within the range [45, 75], the bonus is at least £0.5.
- If the slider for "if-white-bet" stays within the range [25, 55], the bonus is at least £0.5.
- If the slider for "if-red-bet" stays within the range [35, 45], the bonus is £1.5.

Submit

Round 1 out of 14

Task 1. Choose color compositions for Box L and Box R

Box L: 120 Balls **Box R: 80 Balls** **Box A: 200 Balls**

step: 3 step: 5

The current composition of Box A is:

81	39	5	75

Show balls Snapshot

Confirm color composition

Task 2. Bet on the label of "Ball A" if knowing its color

If "Ball A" is red, lable is

I bet that its label is:

I think the likelihood of its label being L vs. R is:

L: 86% R: 14%

If "Ball A" is white, lable is

I bet that its label is:

I think the likelihood of its label being L vs. R is:

L: 33% R: 67%

Next Round

Your payment

The random round is 1. Here are your choices in this round.

Box L: 120 Balls

Box R: 80 Balls

"Ball A" has been drawn from Box A:
 L R

The mathematician thinks the likelihood of its label being L vs. R is:
L: 34% R: 66%

The current composition of Box A is:

<input checked="" type="radio"/> L	<input type="radio"/> L	<input checked="" type="radio"/> R	<input type="radio"/> R
81	39	5	75

If "Ball A" is white, I bet that its label is:
 L R

I think the likelihood of its label being L vs. R is:
L: 33% R: 67%

Your total Payment is: £15.50

= £4.00 for showing up + £10.00 for your bet choice + £1.50 for your likelihood estimation.

Please share us thoughts about how you make the color and the bet choices:

Confirm